

CONCEPT OF ARITHMETIC PROGRESSION

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Abstract: This article describes the concept of arithmetic progression. The essence of progression is explained with the help of simple examples.

Keywords: arithmetic progression, n-term, sum, difference of n terms.

Arithmetic progression is a series of numbers in which each number, starting from the second number, is formed by adding a constant number d (the difference of the progression) to the previous number for this series.

The series is written n the number of units (in them among equal too be can) of length n that is equal to the sequence is called and is as follows, is determined:

a1, a2, ..., an

In mathematics, infinite series, as well as also regarded. For example: the natural number sequence, pair, or an odd number of a sequence and so on.

If an+1 - 1 had had the previous (through, for example, an through had) the expression of elections, this series of recurrent method given is called. Thus, the initial a few had given the need

This xn+2 = xn+1 + xn recurrent form with given series Fibonachchi the number of sequence is called. Thus, x1 and x2 given had will have to lish.

For example: 1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 13, 21, ...

Fibonachchi the number of sequence to any natural n at the following equality:

x1 + x2 + x3 + ... + xn = xn+2 + x2

Thus, x1 and x2 s previously given the number of

You are a1, a2, ..., an, ... is the sequence of all natural number n s of an+1 = an + d is equal to, if carried out, such series arifmetik progression is called, d-scratch in contrast, any number

d = an+1 - an is the number of arithmetic progression of is called an = a1 + d · (n - 1) expression progression arithmetic n-had or total had called

1-texture: Arithmetic progression had for an = (an-k + an+k) / 2 equality. Thus, for n > k, k ∈ N. "Arithmetic progression," the name also that come out

2-texture: m, n, l, k natural number for m + n = l + k equal to from am + an = a1 + ak equal come out

Arithmetic progression of the first n units terms:

Sn = a1 + a2 + a3 + ... + an

Sn = (a1 + an) · n / 2 or Sn = (2a1 + d(n-1)) · n / 2, thus

If $d = 0$ to, $S_n = a_1 \cdot n$

$S_n - S_{n-1} = a_n$ equality.

Let's get acquainted with the following issue:

Example-1:

Balls are drawn in a triangular shape so that 1 in the 1st row, 2 in the 2nd row, 3 in the 3rd row, etc. If there are 120 balls in total, how many rows are there?

How many balls are needed to make 30 "row" triangles?

Solution: From the condition of the problem, we find that $a_1=1$ and $d=1$. Then we need to find n from the equation $S_n=120$.

$$120 = (2 \cdot 1 + 1 \cdot (n - 1)) / 2 \cdot n \rightarrow n^2 + n - 240 = 0 \rightarrow n = 15$$

In the next condition of the problem, $n=30$, we need to find S_{30} .

$$S_{30} = (2 \cdot 1 + 1 \cdot (30 - 1)) / 2 \cdot 30 = 31 \cdot 15 = 465$$

In conclusion, it is worth noting that the concept of sequences and arithmetic progression is considered vital, and mastering the progression will serve as an important factor in our future lifestyle and application in life, as can be seen in the example of the above issues.

References:

1. Self. The first volume. Tashkent, 2000.
2. Shakhmeister A. H. Progressions. Arithmetic progression // Sets. Functions. Sequences. Progressions: book / A. Kh. Shakhmeister, ed. ed. B. G. Ziva. — 2nd ed., corrected. and additional - St. Petersburg. : "Petroglyph" : "Victoria Plus" ; M. : MTSNMO Publishing House, 2008. - S. 141. - 296 p. : illus. - (Mathematics. Elective courses). - 3000 copies.
3. Abduxamidov S., Abduxamidova N. MENTAL ARITHMETIC: THE ART OF SKILL //O'rta Osiyo ta'lim va innovatsiyalar jurnali. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 128-130.
4. Sh. Alimov, O. Kholmukhamedov, M. Mirzaahmedov. 9th grade Algebra textbook, Tashkent-2019.
5. DTM's set of 2019 test tasks in Mathematics
6. Bronstein I. N., Semendyaev K. A. Handbook of mathematics for engineers and students of higher educational institutions. — M.: Nauka, 1986. — 544 p.

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7. Arithmetic progression // Encyclopedic Dictionary of Brockhaus and Efron: in 86 volumes (82 volumes and 4 additional). - St. Petersburg, 1890. - T. II. - S. 98.
8. www.ziyonet.uz
9. www.kitob.uz
10. www.arxiv.uz

